

MODERN EDUCATIONAL METHODS IN TEACHING MOTHER LANGUAGE LESSONS

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Abstract. This article describes the methods of teaching mother tongue. Various methods have been analyzed.

Key words: mother tongue, method, travel method, lesson, student, knowledge, exercise method, interview method.

The fact that the knowledge given to students in the mother tongue classes is built mainly on a theoretical basis in the following years leads to the lowering of practical skills. The lesson is mainly limited to memorizing the learned rule and giving an example from the textbook and doing exercises.

During the lesson, only the textbook is used. As a result, the teacher remains a textbook teacher, and the student remains a textbook student. Because of this, students are not able to fulfill the requirements outside of the textbook, they do not understand that life itself is an example and a rule. Therefore, it is necessary to pay attention to the development of the foundations of formation of practical knowledge. For this purpose, it is necessary to give tasks aimed at increasing students' vocabulary, teaching them to work on vocabulary, forming correct pronunciation norms and developing their ability to think and think. Currently, non-traditional teaching methods are used, encouraging students to actively participate in each lesson. This teaching method is currently showing its positive effect in various places.

The most used method in mother tongue lessons is the teacher's narration method. With the help of narration, more complex topics, especially those that were not

previously known to students, are explained. Also, the narrative method is used to explain the meaning of grammatical definitions, provide additional information to students, and answer their questions. If it is related to the previously learned material, the conversation method is used in the lesson. Conversation increases students' activity. Under the guidance of the teacher, they observe, compare and discuss the evidence, and then draw a general conclusion. Conversation is one of the important factors in developing students' speech culture. There are 3 types of conversation: informational conversation, heuristic conversation, conversation to reinforce the topic. If more than one section is studied in refresher lessons, or at the end of the quarter, at the end of the year, lessons are organized with more students working on their own.

In order to consolidate what has been learned, it is also said to solve the test questions. In the revision lesson at the end of the year, almost all students create test questions and cross-examinations. The lesson will be more lively and interesting. The method of observing language evidence is widely used in studying the written language of grammar and orthography. When analyzing language facts, three directions are taken as a basis.

Observing language evidence. Under the guidance of the teacher, students conduct observations on some aspect of language phenomena based on a specific plan.

Method of exercises.

Students' knowledge and skills acquired in their mother tongue are strengthened through various exercises.

As a result, students:

- a) learn knowledge consciously;
- b) will be able to apply knowledge in practice;
- c) thinking skills also increase, they observe, compare, and summarize language evidence more during the exercise;
- g) they will have the opportunity to improve their speech culture.

Exercises improve students' understanding and learning activities gradually: they begin to master certain facts by memorization. It also happens that by writing a lot, the student develops the ability to correctly support certain word forms or punctuation marks. Exercises are conducted on the basis of a strict system. First, students work on the text, group words and sentences. These are exercises in understanding grammatical forms. In schools, such types of exercises as choosing examples, working on drawings, changing the form of the text are held. "Travel" method. The travel method is more widely used in the subjects of history, geography, biology, and literature. Travel provides more material for writing an essay, so the reader, for example, in a museum, pays special attention to the object and its symbols that are relevant to the content of the essay, and it is necessary to write down the words that express these concepts. The travel method can be used to study the topic "Words specific to dialect" with 5th grade students. As a result of working with each student separately, it will be possible to repeat and consolidate what has been learned.

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